

Formation of National Identity among Children in Southern Nigeria and the Analysis of their Attitude of In-group/Out-group: An Experimental Study

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The paper examined the dynamics of socializing southern Nigerian children amidst prevailing ethno-religious conflicts claiming lives and properties in the northern Nigeria; the consequences of the realities on in-group attitude and out-group attitude of the children were analysed. The study adopted an experimental design and was conducted in a classroom among 55 primary school pupils in Lagos, Southern Nigeria. Results suggested that Southern Nigerian children hold favourable attitudes towards their in-group, but showed unfavourable attitudes towards their fellow children in northern Nigeria (out-group), essentially, due to the prevailing crises in the area; consequently, they expressed a negative national identity. The implication of these findings on the quest for a cohesive national life in Nigeria and other African countries was discussed.

Keyword: Identity formation, Southern Nigeria, in-group, out-group, attitude.

Nigeria is made up of over 250 ethnic nationalities. Yoruba and Igbo are the major ethnic groups in the south, while Hausa and Fulani are the major ethnic groups in the North. Prior to the amalgamation of Nigeria in 1914, the British had administered the whole country as Northern and Southern protectorates. Then, in 1960, the British granted independence to Nigeria and became an entity with diverse ethnic groups. Many economic and political events have transpired between independence and the present day Nigeria. She has experienced a civil war between 1967 and 1970, she has been (mis)ruled by military at different times, she had witnessed oil boom that unleashed unprecedented prosperity but later brought her many woes. (Ayokhai, 2010). When Nigeria became independent, it came with pong and pageantry, hopes were high, nationalism was at the peak, there was a lot of patriotism, it was not difficult to construct a positive national identity. However, positive affect for out-group among many ethnic groups in Nigeria began to give way for mistrust and suspicion, which has its root in perceived unfair distribution of natural resources, this challenge has led to formulation and

reformulation of sharing formula. This scenario seems to support the claim of Bannon and Collier (1997) that nations endowed with natural resources are prone to violent conflicts. That Northern part of Nigeria has been particularly notorious for religious induced violent conflicts is to state the obvious, just when Nigeria thought it was getting over the burden of militancy attacks from the youths of Niger Delta, that characterized the fourth republic under President Olusegun Obasanjo, through the success of the amnesty programme, introduced by his successor, Late Musa Yaradua. (Ekpo, 2004), the country was rudely confronted with fresh hostilities from a religious group called Boko Haram. Hundreds of Nigerians have lost lives and properties since the beginning of these insurgencies, at the moment over 200 school-girls have been abducted with no clues to their whereabouts.

“It is a long story, they came to our school and deceived us into believing they were soldiers, they were dressed in military uniform and made us believe they were about rescuing us only for us to later find out that they were

insurgents, when we discovered it was already too late and there was little we could do” (The Punch Newspaper, April, 2014).

Apart from these political and security challenges, Nigerians have had to grapple with harsh economic condition, social insecurity; unemployment is, presently, at over 23.9 percent (National Bureau of Statistics, as cited in Trading Economics, 2014). Poverty rate is at all time high and this may account for the feeling of despair and disenchantments among many Nigerians. Some are beginning to ask for a review of the union as a country, hence the setting up of a national conference by the current administration, headed by President Goodluck Jonathan, for a national dialogue, in spite of this initiative by the government, many Nigerians are still doubtful about their future in Nigeria. (The Punch Newspaper’s opinion poll, April, 2014).

This cycle of negative experiences appear to be affecting the socialization process of Southern Nigerian children. It shows that many parents in southern Nigeria are facing the herculean task of making children internalize the virtues of love for the nation and fellow Nigerians, particularly from the Northern part. how can they possibly make their children imbibe the virtues of love, tolerance, and trust, when they are daily bombarded with news of attacks on their relatives who reside in the north, moreover, what would the children make of portraits of hate through violence being daily reported in Nigeria print and electronic media? Against this backdrop, this study aims to investigate how southern Nigerian children are constructing a national identity. What is the present social reality for the internalization of national pride? How does a Nigerian child from the southern part of the country perceive children of the northern part of the country i.e, is there a positive in-group attitude and negative out-group attitude in southern Nigerian children? This is what this study sets out to investigate.

Identity Formation: A theoretical Framework.

There are several meanings that can be found in the literature on identity formation, this is so because, it has been studied in various academic disciplines such as philosophy, sociology, psychology, anthropology, *e.t.c*, (Rynanen, 2002), The perspectives can be categorized under the following headings; Psychodynamic perspective, Social Interactionism perspective, Social identity perspective and social-cultural perspective. however, this research is largely guided by socio cultural theory, this paper aligns its position with this theory, particularly as proposed by Vygotsky (1997), because of its focus on the process right from childhood period, and its emphasis on the impact of social context, nevertheless , an overview of these other related theories is done before zeroing in on socio-cultural theory,

Psychodynamic theory was pioneered by Erikson (1968). According to Erikson, identity is constructed as a consequence of biological and psychological maturation and each stage in the process has its own characteristics regarding the individual’s interaction with his or her environment. Erickson outlined a chronological and changing concept of identity. He argued that, identity is not something one has, but something that develops during one’s whole life. He therefore developed eight stages of identity development based on psychodynamic theory.

In Social interactionism, Mead (1934) used the concept of identity in relationship with the concept of self; he explained that the self is developed through transactions with the environment. He explained that communication plays a crucial role in identity formation. i.e., identity is negotiated and re-negotiated through dialogues, in making sense of his view of the intrinsically, social nature of human beings whereby the self evolves within individual’s social interaction, and the process continues through the life of human being.

According to Vygotsky (1981), who laid the foundation for socio-cultural perspective on identity, identity is shaped through cognitive development and the cultural context in which individuals live. He emphasized the potentials of words as

tools and social interaction as the context in which individuals are exposed to form and come to use them. He argued that language and other signs are intrinsically related to mental process, e.g thinking. He called the process through which thoughts are formed in language and verbalized as words as inner speech. In Vygotsky's view, individuals use speech not only for social communication but also to guide, plan and monitor their behavior. Vygotsky said that language and thought initially developed independently of each other and then merge. He suggested that all mental functions have external or social origins. Children must use language to communicate with others before they can focus inwards on their own thoughts. Vygotsky further argued that children who use private speech are more socially competent than those who do not. In the light of Vygotsky's theory, socialization process for children is facilitated by oral communication. Based on this theoretical proposition this study believes that southern Nigerian parents are communicating suspicion, fear and hate to children about Nigerian in the northern part due to their frustrations of perceived unfair distribution of resources between the north and the south and the ethno-religious violence being constantly perpetrated by the northern insurgents.

Bakhtin (1981) somewhat hold similar view with Vygotsky, for him, Identity is a socio-historical product in interaction. The self that reflects upon its activity is different from the self that acts. To be understood by others, people have to cast themselves in terms of the other, and they do that by seeing themselves from outside. Bakhtin writes about "The space of authorities", implying differences between a neophyte and a person of greater experience, who begins to rearrange, reword, rephrase, orchestrate different voices and by this process, develops his/her own "authorial stance". "One's own discourse and one's own voice, although born of another or dynamically stimulated by another, will sooner or later begin to liberate themselves from the authority of other's discourse" (Bakhtin 1981). This position reinforces my belief in the impact of socialization that

is initiated and facilitated by older persons who have become disillusioned by social experiences such as ethnic and religious militancy.

Literature Review

Children and their in-group/Out-group attitude

On the premise of socio-cultural theory, human beings move through the socialization process within the group context to which they found themselves, this enables them to acquire defined attitudes towards other human beings. (Fagbohunge & Longe, 2010). Attitude is a learned evaluative reaction to persons or objects. It is a learned predisposition to act in a consistent evaluative manner (Wittig, 1977). It can be viewed as the favourableness or unfavourableness with which a human perceive other humans, this implies that one can have a positive and a negative attitude towards others. (Fagbohunge & Longe, 2010).

One form of negative attitude towards out-group is prejudice. Prejudice is a preconceived idea about people, perceived as being different due to race, religion, culture, gender, disabilities, appearance, language, sexual orientation and culture (Byrnes, 1995). It is a learned reaction that is overgeneralised and unjustified. It comes from making prejudgments about others without adequate facts. Learning theorists believe that prejudice is learned in the same way other attitudes and values are learned, primarily, through association, reinforcement and modeling (Akindipe & Asekun, 2007). There is a considerable large amount of literature on prejudice among children, however the conceptualization is usually premised on the assumption that the prejudice was usually directed to minority group members, this paper however argues that prejudice does not necessarily have to come from ethnic majority children and the children have their own 'justifiable reason' for holding these negative opinions about the out-group.

Adorno, Frenkel-Brunswik, Leevinso & Sanford (1950) submitted that the acquisition of prejudice can be linked to the development of a particular personality

type, the Authoritarian Personality, this view is influenced by Freudian thinking. However, Horowitz & Horowitz (1938) believe that children's prejudices reflect the attitudes and values of the community they come from. That children just learn the negative attitudes towards the particular ethnic groups through their parents and those around them. There is substantial evidence in literature that there is a positive correlation between ethnic attitudes of children and their parents (Bird, Monachesi, & Burdick, 1952; Horowitz & Horowitz, 1938). According to socio-cognitive perspective, a child's attitude is dependent on the level of cognitive development and process (Aboud, 1988). This development according to this position occurs in sequences. One sequence involves a child being dominated by affective-perceptual process associated with unknown fear and being attached to what is familiar. The next in the sequence is the development is concrete operational development which is concerned with dominant with preference to child's in-group and a rejection of the out-group which is usually determined by physical attributes such as skin colour, language, body size e.t.c., overlapping this sequence is the other stage of development which brings about a change in the focus of a child's attention to liking individuals for their personal qualities rather than the group qualities. It has come to be accepted that cognitive development changes can be implicated in the acquisition and expression of numerous behaviours (Durkin, 1995), the perspective fails to make clarifications on the possibility that children can develop long-lasting prejudices in the absence of any negative contact with an ethnic minority group member (Brown, 1995).

Social identity perspective places emphases on social; motivational consideration and awareness of social structure. (Tajfel & Turner, 1979), according to this view, prejudice and discrimination towards members of out-groups is a function of an individual's quest to identify with social groups which are considered to be positively distinctive or comparatively superior to other groups for

the purpose of boosting their own self esteem. The resultant effect of group identification is that in-group members are perceived to be similar and possess desirable qualities and hence are subject to favourable bias, on the contrary, out-group members are perceived to be different and possess less desirable attributes and therefore may attract prejudice and discrimination. Aboud (1988) suggested that in-group bias and out-group prejudice increase to a peak around age 7 when the group differences become prominent, but with a subsequent growth in the child's cognitive abilities arising from the concrete operational thinking around age 7, Aboud is of the view that there arises a systematic decline in group-based biases, which is further improved by the child's ever increasing cognitive abilities that allow him/her to attend to the differences between individuals. Some studies also reported that rather than prejudice reducing during primary school years, it actually remains at the same level from the age of 7 until the age of 12 years (Banks & Rompf, 1973), but some other studies reported that it increases in those years. (Vaughan & Thompson, 1962, Bartel, Bartel & Grill, 1973). Nesdale (2004) posited that children who show prejudice had gone through four sequential stages which comprise: Undifferentiated, ethnic awareness, ethnic preference and ethnic prejudice.

According to him these stages are differentiated in terms of the behaviour which characterizes them and events which initiates changes from one stage to the next. He further explained that in the first phase i.e, Undifferentiated stage, racial clues are typically not salient to children, they respond to stimuli, which include unfamiliar people, on a largely random basis in terms of what attract their attention, they can discriminate colours among other attributes of inanimate objects. Nesdale also suggested that at the second phase which he labels Ethnic Awareness: a child (usually around the age of 3), develops ethnic awareness, this is particularly so if he or she lives in an heterogeneous society, this is consistent with the findings of Stevenson and Stevenson, (1960); Goodman (1964). At the

third phase, which is ethnic preference stage Nesdale explained that the child learns and understands that he belongs to a particular ethnic group, thus making him to focus on the in-group rather than the out-group, the emphasis here, according to him is that self-identification does not necessarily instigate an out-group focus with out-group dislike, it mainly activates a focus on, and accompanying preference for the in-group. Nesdale insisted that self identification merely facilitates a growing understanding of the social structure in the community, the status of the divers groups and their interrelationships. At the fourth phase which is Ethnic Prejudice, Nesdale opposed the view of Aboud (1988) that ethnic prejudice diminishes from 7 years onward, he argued that at this period prejudice actually crystallizes and emerges the children who hold such attitudes. This position appears to have a lot of support in current literature.

Method

2 boys were engaged to act fighting a physical combat (after getting the consent of their parents and their own consent to participate in the experiment.) The two boys were of Yoruba ethnic group in Southern Nigeria. One of the two boys was, however, dressed like a northerner, while the other boy wore an English, casual, T-shirt which is what is commonly wore by children in the south . During the fight, the “Hausa” spoke pidgin English with the northerner assent by accusing the boy of stealing his money. The other boy spoke back in Yoruba Language. Again, the Hausa boy looked smaller and shorter, while the Yoruba boy was bigger and taller, this was done deliberately to see if it would influence the attitude of the video viewers in favour of the northern boy. This was then recorded in a video. It was about three minute’s video. However the beginning of the fight was not showed and so nobody could tell from watching the video that actually started the fight. Fifty-five (55) children were thereafter selected through a random sampling as participants in the study. Being a field-experimental design, the study was conducted in classrooms of pupils between the age of 9 years and 10 years. They were

also, mainly children from southern Nigeria. The children were showed the video. After watching the video, Participants were administered with a questionnaire with 15 question items. Part A asked questions on demography, Part B asked questions on perceived ethnic affiliations of the two boys who fought in the video, and the questionnaire also sought to know who between the two boys was believed to have started the fight and why they believe so. Then, they were required to describe each of the two boys with an adjective (‘good’, ‘bad’.) Finally, the last section, i.e. section C, which were 5 question items sought to measure the views of the participants on national identity. The scale was adapted from National identification scale originally developed by Billiet & Leuven (2008).

Hypothesis

- i) Southern Nigerian children would assume that the starter of any fight (involving a southerner and a northerner) is a northerner
- ii) Children would describe out-group member with a negative word.
- iii) Children would describe in-group member with a positive word
- iv) Nigerian Children have a negative national identity

Results

The data was analysed using descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. The total number of participants was 55 drawn from two classes, Primary 5 and 6. With the average age of 9, 29 of them were males while the remaining 26 were females. 54 of the children come from southern Nigeria, the 55th child did not indicate where he/she comes from. 38 representing 70.4 percent claimed they have travelled out of their city at one time or another but not northern Nigeria, while 16 representing 29.6 percent of the children have never travelled in their lives. After watching the video, 47 of the children representing 85.5 percent indicated that the boy wearing brown dress come from North, only 5 children believe

that the boy in brown was a southerner, while the remaining three did not indicate. In the same vain, 49 pupils representing 89.1 percent thought that the boy in blue dress come from south, only 3 believe he

was a northerner while the remaining 3 failed to indicate.

Hypothesis 1

Southern children would assume that the starter of any fight (involving a northerner and a southerner) is a northerner

Table 1: Summary of the Regression analysis showing the effect of the part of the country on attitude to out-group member

I.V	D.V	R2	B		T	P
Part of the country (South)	Attitude to Out-group	0.08	-0.296	-0.087	7.248	<.05

Table 1 shows the extent to which the part of the country the child comes from influences his/her attitude to the out-group member. The R Square = 0.08, which implies that the proportion of the variance accounted for by the model is 0.08%. Moreover, P< .05 which shows that the model is significant. This hereby confirms

the hypothesis that the southern children would assume that the starter of any fight (involving a northerner and a southerner) is a northerner.

ii) Children would describe out-group member with a negative word.

Table 2: Summary of the Regression analysis showing the effect of ethnic affiliation on attitude to out-group member

I.V	D.V	R2	B		T	P
Ethnic Origin. (South)	Description of out -group	0.07	0.264	0.081	8.061	<.05

Table 2 also shows the extent to which the part of the country the child comes from influences his/her attitude to the out-group member. The R Square = 0.07, which implies that the proportion of the variance accounted for by the model is 0.07%. Moreover, P<.05 which shows that the

model is significant. It therefore confirms the hypothesis that the southern children would describe out-group member with a negative word.

ii) Children would describe in-group member with a positive word.

Table 3: Summary of the Regression analysis showing the effect of ethnic affiliation on attitude to in -group member

I.V	D.V	R2	B		T	P
Ethnic Origin. (South)	Description of In -group	.013	-.241	-.032	8.345	<.05

Table 3 also shows the extent to which ethnic the part of the country the child comes from influences his attitude to the out-group member. The R Square = 0.13, which implies that the proportion of the variance accounted for by the model

is 0.13%. Moreover, $P < .05$ which shows that the model is significant. the hypothesis is hereby retained that the southern children would describe out-group member with a positive word.

Table 4: Southern Nigerian Children have a negative national identity.

Crosstabulation

Count	I am willing to live all my life in Nigeria				Total
	very much	Much	i don't know	not much	
What part of Nigeria are you from?					
South	6	4	15	29	54
North	0	0	1	0	1
Total	6	4	16	29	55

In the table above, only 6 children very much desire and only 4 desire much to live all their lives as Nigerians in Nigeria. 16 of the children do not know, while the majority which is 29 in numbers does not much want to live in Nigeria. This result suggests that southern Nigerian children have negative national identity.

Discussion and conclusion

Hypothesis one which states that Southern children would assume that the starter of any fight (involving a northerner and a southerner) is a northerner was tested and confirmed. Apart from the written responses that constituted the obtained data, most of the pupils, in their characteristic manners, were heard during the experiment making comments such as “the northerners are always looking for trouble” “ they are Boko Haram people causing troubles everywhere”. The result is consistent with the findings of Starvindes & Panayiotis (2013) who reported that Greek-Cypriot children confirmed an expected in-group favouritism, this deduction was made by these researchers by alluding to the role of socio-historical factor in the socialization process of these children. Thus supporting the assumption of the learning theorists who believe that negative attitude is learned in the same way behaviours and values are learned primarily through association, reinforcement and modeling which have their basis in a social setting. However, this study rejects the view that negative attitude to out-group is often expressed by

a majority ethnic group to affirm their superiority against a minority group as suggested by Tajfel & Turner (1979). Rather, it supports the notion that prejudices can be expressed by children to out-group, irrespective of its status-whether majority or minority, the determinant in my view, is the kind of socialization process and the personal social experience of the children in their social setting as the study founds out. The children who participated in this study apart from possibly learning their negative attitudes through socialization are also witnessing for themselves the experience of militancy in the north, they have been directly or indirectly affected as their cousins and relatives who live in the northern Nigeria have become victims in one way or another.

The outcome of the test on hypothesis two and three, which showed that children would describe out-group member with a negative word, and would describe in-group member with a positive word, are in line with the view of Brown (1995) as cited in Nesdale (2008) that the tendency for children to develop ethnic prejudices increases as suspicion, disagreement, tension and conflict increases between members of the dominant and ethnic minority groups. Nesdale reported that the observation was based on studies with adult, and acknowledged that studies among children to prove this point was lacking. This study can be said to fill this important gap. As earlier pointed out in this

paper, that in the present day Nigeria, there is so much animosity among the ethnic groups, there is ethnic rivalry coupled with, religious extremism in northern part of Nigeria, this development has taken a toll on the healthy relationship between the people of the south and those of the north and consequently is robbing off on the attitudes of the children in the country.

Hypothesis four which states that Nigerian Southern Nigerian Children have a negative national Identity supports the position of Billiet & Leuven (2008) who stated that the saliency of an identity (ethnic or national) is not stable but is dependent on situations and contexts. It is indeed social circumstances of a people that would be a determinant of whether a people would develop negative or positive national identity. In the study there is avalanche of evidence that the social circumstance of Nigerian children has been an unpleasant one, hence the development of the negative national identity by the children.

National integration would remain a mirage if things remain the way they are in Nigeria, if peaceful co-existence is not seriously pursued as a goal by government of Nigeria the fragile peace may become worsened. At the moment it seems that national cohesion is lacking and this is affecting several institutions in the country. Several Institutions' ability to perform their mandate is increasingly being challenged because of their weak state which is occasioned by negative attitudes of individuals towards their compatriots working together. It was recently reported that there were sabotages within the army who feed insurgents with information about the army. These are some of the consequences of mistrust among different ethnic groups in Nigeria. People of Nigeria must look again objectively into the basis of their union. Different ethnic nationalities must be carried along in the governance of the nation; moreover, there must be a fair and equitable distribution of resources among different part of Nigeria with a view to minimize the feelings of injustice among the different ethnic groups comprising Nigeria. With these recommendations, Nigerian parents would have good reason to live peacefully with other Nigerians in any

part of the country and also make their children imbibe the virtues of love and tolerance, having the favourable attitude towards others in any part of the country. This principle in my view, is also applicable to other African countries having similar challenges

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